

Constant Speed as a Clock, Energy, Classical Special Relativity, Quantum Mechanical Photon

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. Oct. 1, 2025

It is possible to create some clocks by introducing an initial amount of energy (i.e. doing some work). Examples include a pendulum and spring, but we argue that a particle with constant speed also represents a clock and requires some initial energy to be created. It is thus possible to have a constant speed representing one kind of clock and then “add” a velocity component to create a new clock. As an example, one may consider a clock based on a constant velocity in an object at rest, and then move the entire object, hence adding a velocity component to the already existing velocity to create a new clock.

If one has the special case that there exists a v_y in the rest frame and one adds a v_x , but the magnitude of velocity remains constant, then one is guaranteed different time intervals for the two clocks if distances are different, as they are. In other words, one would show that a clock in a rest frame of a moving object is not the same as the clock seen from the rest frame. This is well known in special relativity.

From Maxwell's electromagnetic equations, there exists an object which has the same speed in different frames, namely light moving in a vacuum. Furthermore, Maxwell's solution is linked with $-Et+px$ or $c = E/p$. Given that an object at rest requires work to set it into motion and that a photon may be part of rest mass, one would expect a photon in the moving object to be seen as having a different energy with respect to the lab frame. In the rest frame of the moving object: $x/t = c$ and $E=pc$, but seen from a rest frame, $x'/t' = c$ and $E'=p'c$. We argue that this implies a direct relationship between E' , p' and x',t' which is a quantum mechanical notion.

In both the photon and particle with rest mass cases, $-Et+px = \text{constant}$. In the photon case, the constant is zero so the built-in ruler and clock gradations, when divided, yield the speed c . In the particle with rest mass case, one still has a built-in ruler and clock, but the ratio of the gradations does not give speed v , which is fine. There is no a priori reason for the quotient to yield the speed.

The Notion of a Clock

Consider a particle with rest mass at rest at some x_1 point. Although one may have a clock present, one may also have a situation with no clock as the clock is not describing any changes. If, however, one wishes to have the rest particle move from x_1 to x_2 , then Newton's first law implies that a force must be applied and work done. Because there is a sequence x_1 to x_2 , the notion of time is required and in fact, the constant speed represents a clock as there is a repeated Δx for a given Δt . Thus, one may see that a constant speed may represent a clock as well as a ruler and that an initial amount of energy is required to create this clock-ruler system.

Other examples of clocks which require an initial amount of energy to create them include a pendulum and a spring.

Given that a clock may be represented by a constant speed, one may change the speed by doing work and create a new clock. This has interesting consequences because one may have

a speed clock in an object at rest. One may then do work on this object to give it an overall speed, hence changing the speed clock as seen from a rest frame. This raises the possibility of having different times in different frames, something not considered before special relativity.

Clocks in Frames Distinguished by Different Speeds

As an example, one may ask: Is there an object which has the same speed as seen in different frames moving with constant speed relative to each other? Having the same speed in each frame means that one does not simply have scaling of:

$$d = vt \quad ((0))$$

Rather, if the speed is the same in each frame, but distances are different for the same physical event, then times are different too.

There does seem to be an object with the same speed in different frames (moving at constant speed with respect to each other) based on Maxwell's solution for a photon from his electromagnetic equations. In particular, he obtains the speed c for a photon in a vacuum, whether it is moving in a rest frame or seen from a moving frame. Furthermore, Maxwell's solution for a photon makes use of $-Et + px = 0$ implying that:

$$E = pc \quad \text{photon} \quad ((1))$$

Given that a constant speed may be used as a clock, there is no reason not to use c to create such a clock. In particular, one may have a photon moving along the y axis from an origin to a point Δy . Then a time interval is given by:

$$\Delta y = c \Delta t_1 \quad ((2))$$

If this clock exists in an object at rest, which is then set in motion along the x axis with speed v , the photon moves at an angle as seen in the lab frame (watching the moving system) with:

$$\Delta x = v \Delta t_2 \quad ((3a))$$

$$\Delta y = c \Delta t_1 \quad ((3b))$$

Thus, c is the same, but length is different, so Δt_1 and Δt_2 must be different. In fact, as is already well-known from special relativity:

$$c \Delta t_2 = c \sqrt{v^2 \Delta t_2^2 + c^2 \Delta t_1^2} \quad \text{or:}$$

$$\Delta t_1 = \Delta t_2 / \sqrt{1 - v^2/c^2} \quad ((4))$$

Energy Considerations

A particle with constant speed acts as a clock (and ruler too), but work (creation energy) is needed to create this clock, just as initial energy (work) is needed to set a pendulum or spring in motion. A clock (photon moving in the y-direction in an object at rest) should then require more energy to create a new clock as seen by an observer in a rest frame, when the entire object is moving.

In particular, a photon has energy which may be considered to be part of the rest mass. If the entire mass is set into motion, then:

$$M_{\text{occ}} \rightarrow m_{\text{occ}}/\sqrt{1-v^2/c^2} \quad ((5))$$

Thus, one does not simply have a new clock (as seen from the lab frame in which the object and its photon clock are moving), but the photon energy should change as well. From Maxwell's solution for a photon:

$$E = pc \quad \text{so} \quad E' = p' c \quad ((6))$$

These equations ((6)) are of the exact same form as $\Delta y = c \Delta t_1$ and $\sqrt{(\Delta x)^2 + (\Delta y)^2} = c \Delta t_2$.

As a result, by analyzing changes to a photon clock, one sees that photon energy and momentum magnitude are directly related to Δt and Δx . In particular:

$$-E\Delta t + p\Delta x \rightarrow \Delta t = \text{constant}/E \quad \text{and} \quad \Delta x = \text{constant}/p \quad ((7))$$

An object moving at a constant speed, like a photon, may be seen to be a clock, and its energy and momentum are related to gradations of this clock through ((7)). It also acts like a ruler.

This is also consistent with a wave picture linked to the electric and magnetic fields, as found by Maxwell.

Particle with Rest Mass

What about a particle with rest mass? If a photon, which moves at a constant speed, acts as a clock, a particle with rest mass moving at a constant speed should also represent a clock, although $E=pc$ and other equations listed above no longer hold. Furthermore:

$$-E\Delta t + p\Delta x = \text{constant} \quad ((8))$$

holds for both a photon and a particle with rest mass. The constant is 0 for a photon, meaning $E=pc$, but it is non-zero for a particle with rest mass. In the photon case, one has:

$$\text{Clock interval} = \text{constant}/E, \quad \text{but also} \quad \Delta x = c \Delta t \quad ((9))$$

There is no a priori reason why intervals Δx and Δt , which apply to a built-in ruler and clock, and follow from ((8)), need to also describe the speed of a particle with rest mass. They happen to describe the speed of a photon because $m_0=0$. As a result, a particle with rest mass may still represent a clock with E and p being linked to clock and ruler gradations through ((7)) and have a speed v not given by $\Delta x / \Delta t = p/E$.

We suggest that one may see free particle-photon quantum mechanics emerge in this manner by considering a particle with constant speed as a clock as well as a ruler and using ((8)) to find a quantitative expression. Free particle quantum mechanics seems to be strongly linked to special relativity as we have argued in previous notes.

Conclusion

In conclusion, a key idea of this note is to consider an object (photon, particle with rest mass), moving at constant speed, as a clock (and ruler). To create this clock, one must provide an initial amount of energy, just like an initial energy (work) is needed to set a pendulum or spring in motion.

We specifically consider the case of a photon clock (photon moving in the y direction) in an object at rest. If initial work is done to move this object to a constant speed v in the x direction, then the photon clock is converted into a different clock as seen by a person in the lab (watching the moving object). Because the speed of light c is the same as seen in both frames (as a consequence of Maxwell's derivation of a photon from his electromagnetic equations), one may directly link Δt_1 (y -direction photon) to Δt_2 , new photon clock, through: $c \Delta t_2 = c \sqrt{c^2 \Delta t_1^2 + v^2 \Delta t_1^2}$. The result is the well-known one of special relativity.

We further note that to create such a new clock means adding energy. In the photon case, one has $E=pc$ and $E'=p'c$ because even though c is the same in both frames, physically one must do work on the object (with the y -photon clock) at rest and so the photon's energy should change. We argue that in the photon case, there must be a link between the new clock and energy. In particular, $\Delta t_2 = c \Delta x_2$ and $E'=p'c$ and for the y -photon clock, $\Delta t_1 = c \Delta x_1$ and $E=pc$. Considering this, together with $-Et+px = 0$ from Maxwell, seems to indicate that for a photon: $\Delta x = \text{constant}/p$ and $\Delta t = \text{constant}/E$. A photon, moving at constant speed, seems to represent both a clock and ruler. We suggest that these ideas should carry over to a particle with rest mass, as $-Et+px=\text{constant}$, but the constant is not 0. This simply means that the ruler and clock gradations, when divided, do not give v , the speed of the particle, but there is no a priori reason that it should for one to still have a built-in clock and ruler.